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Topic: Future of Value-Based Care

The Future of Value-Based Care in the United States: Challenges, Opportunities, and Policy Roadmap

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Abstract

Value-Based Care (VBC) has emerged as a transformative approach in U.S. healthcare, prioritizing quality and cost-effectiveness over volume-based reimbursement. This paper reviews current VBC models, their impact on access to care, coverage expansion, and the reduction of disparities related to age, gender, race, and pre-existing conditions. While pilot programs and large-scale implementations have shown promise, significant challenges remain including complex payment landscapes, administrative barriers for late-adopting providers, and persistent physician burnout. Through policy analysis and literature synthesis, this paper identifies opportunities for refinement, such as streamlined reimbursement models, legislative simplification, and support mechanisms for providers transitioning to VBC. Recommendations are provided to guide the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services and other stakeholders in optimizing payment systems for sustainable, equitable, and high-quality healthcare delivery. The findings underscore the importance of aligning financial incentives with patient-centered outcomes to ensure the long-term success of value-based care. ^{10,12,13}

Keywords

Value-Based Care; Healthcare Policy; U.S. Healthcare Reform; Payment Models;
Reimbursement Reform; Medicare and Medicaid; Physician Burnout

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Executive Summary:

Health care in the United States has made a significant impact on improving and extending lives. However, there has been overwhelming evidence that could lessen cost while outcomes could be improved drastically. Pilot projects are being conducted all over the country, addressing these issues, and larger groups have even adopted some. Many approaches can be very beneficial, but which are either underpaid, reimbursed, or not reimbursed at all, including team-based approaches, systems to coordinate care, virtual and wireless services, and home- and community-based interventions, which can prevent hospitalizations. Traditional services receive a higher volume and intensity due to fee-for-service payments. The development, implementation, and evaluation of a range of financing reforms have begun among health plans and providers to support innovative, less-costly care. To provide greater support for delivering high-quality and cost-effective care, these new models use reimbursement rewards value. As a result of these new reimbursement models, providers are better supported for delivering quality care and reducing overall costs by rewarding value instead of volume.^{12,13}

This policy brief shows how a simple motive of having a better quality of care, designed while keeping the patient in the center of the model for beneficial national healthcare, is driven. The care model has positively impacted by improving access, reducing under-insured count, expanding coverage, and reducing discrimination from age, gender, race, previous medical conditions, etc. The negative impacts are the ones we provide recommendations on for it to be better in the future. To support the future of the value-based care (VBC) system, there are certain roadmap designs for the payment methods that need to be looked at by the Center for Medicaid and Medicare Services. With largely developed legislations, programs, and models under the value-based care system, the overall payment landscape has become complicated, the late adopters from the physician's side must undergo administrative barriers and yet

persisting physician burnouts with the current VBC model. We understand the recommendation with its analysis for enhancement of the value-based care model in the coming future. ^{10,12,13}

Policy Brief Description:

Healthcare systems generally take a long time to be developed and be adapted by the general population. As the population ages, people with complex morbidities increase, technological advances are made, citizens' expectations rise, and health expenditures and expectations increase rapidly, this endeavor has become increasingly urgent in most countries. In the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic and its economic repercussions, it will likely be examined again by the public in the wake of health system shocks, such as the global financial crisis of 2007–2008. Several concepts associated with integrating value into health care are developed, including value for money, value-based health care, cost-effectiveness, and patient-reported outcomes. A practical policy framework for value-based policies in health systems is presented in this policy brief to contribute to the discussions about value. An increase in the cost destroys the value of care. This policy brief discusses the history of the birth and the rise of value-based care, the policies revolving around getting an impactful VBC model, and its possible future with certain recommended solutions.¹²

Affecting Policies and History:

Before we take a deep dive into the future of value-based care (VBC), let's first understand how the policies and history of all the value-based care programs and models were developed. There are several value-based care programs currently available in the healthcare market. Over the decade, Medicare has experimented with various such programs since 2008. Let's go through each legislation, program, and model that has been introduced, enhanced, and updated in the value-based care healthcare sector from 2008 to 2021.¹

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Although the first legislation, Medicare Improvements for Patient and Providers Act (MIPPA) initiated in 2008, the word value-based care was first coined in the book "Redefining Health Care" in 2006 by Michael Porter and Elizabeth Olmsted Teisberg. They made sure to convey the premise as, to structure the healthcare model in such a way that it delivers value to the patient. From this derived premise, the patient is in the center of the model, as we see. The healthcare spending in America was rising every year, there was a much-desired need from both the public and the private healthcare payer sector to find ways to slow down this growth. The Healthcare system largely depends on the reimbursement schemes that are being imposed on the populations, the usage of various healthcare services also depends on it. From the early 1990s, this financial issue grew prominent and continued to rise in the 2000s. In 2008, the Centre for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) introduced Medicare Improvements for Patients and Providers (MIPPA).¹ The purpose of this legislation was to provide grants to the tribal locations and help certain Medicare beneficiaries to apply for benefit programs with lower premiums and deductibles. This program later established the End-Stage Renal Disease Quality Incentive Program (ESRD-QIP) in 2012, with quality measures submission and evaluation process. In 2010, the Accountable Care Act (ACA) was passed, by this time, VBC programs showed growth in their size and scope. ACA introduced the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Innovation (CMMI) for the development of VBC programs.¹

Briefly, the Medicare Improvements for Patients and Providers (MIPPA) was introduced in 2008. the Accountable Care Act (ACA) was passed in 2010, and the ACA got value-based care models like

- Pioneer
- Comprehensive Primary Care (CPC+) from 2010 to 2012.

And programs such as,

- End-Stage Renal Disease Quality Incentive Program (ESRD-QIP),

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- Medicare Shared Savings Program (MSSP),
- Hospital Value-Based Purchasing Program (HVBP) and
- Hospital Readmission Reduction Program (HRRP).

In 2014, to save physicians from the then-impending Medicare reimbursement cut of around 24%, Protecting Access to Medicare Act (PAMA) was introduced. It had a program,

- Hospital-Acquired Conditions Reduction Program (HACRP)

In 2015, the Medicare Access and CHIP Reauthorization Act (MACRA) was introduced. The program is included was,

- Merit-Based Incentive Payment System (MIPS)

Impact on Healthcare:

There are many impacts in the value-based care model since the introduction of the Obama Care Act/ Affordable Care Act. The main large-scale impact this policy has got is that it could get 20 million Americans under healthcare insurance coverage. The under-insured population was highlighted during 2016, where only 9% of the total population had healthcare insurance and could pay the premium. This number rose by 20 million since the introduction of ACA. Health insurance marketplaces and the expansion of Medicaid were two of the major provisions of the Affordable Care Act that went into effect in 2014. In addition, the Affordable Care Act's enrollment outreach urged people previously eligible for Medicaid and CHIP to enroll. Currently, Medicaid covers 12.7 million people who were previously eligible for Medicaid and CHIP.⁶

As of October 1, 2010, insurance companies no longer have the option of denying coverage to individuals based on their health status. Most of the population faced discrimination because of their medical history. The health plan providers usually either were unwilling to cover the individual for their existing medical disease or increased the premium rates depending upon this condition. This model suggests the power was in the hand of the healthcare insurance

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company, it seemed more like a revenue-generating model over the healthcare care facility model. As a rule, VBC focuses and keeps patients in the care system's center, the discrimination based on prior medical conditions must be removed. This was successfully done by the introduction of the Affordable Care Act by Value-based Care model. The law banned insurers from having a cap on annual and lifetime limits on the advantages, which averted inadequate financial protection in the case of catastrophic medical events, preventing sickest Americans from availing medical care.⁶

The Medicaid program provides health coverage to low-income children, parents, the elderly, and people with disabilities since its inception, but after the Affordable Care Act, that coverage was extended to adults up to 138 percent of the federal poverty level and 90 percent of the cost was covered by the federal government. Medicaid was expanded in 36 states and Washington D.C., by the Affordable Care Act, covering 12.7 million people. Low-income individuals and their families have proven that having better access to Medicaid has brought them better health options. A larger chunk of data has shown that Medicaid expansion fuels the utilization of various health services, diagnoses, and treatments, such as substance use disorder, cancer, and mental illness. There has been a correlation between Medicare expansion and improved health outcomes such as cardiac surgery and appendicitis hospitalizations. It has also been associated with improvements in mortality rates for patients with heart disease and end-stage renal disease. Aside from improved health outcomes, evidence indicates that Medicaid expansion states have enhanced financial well-being as well, including a reduction in medical debt and improved satisfaction with financial circumstances. Thus, as per the data analysis, we can say that Medicaid isn't bad, it tends to save a life.⁶

In the value-based care system, the healthcare model is designed in a way that certain preventive care activities are free till several visits.³ Preventive healthcare facilities, such as an annual checkup, immunization, dental cleanup, etc. Preventive healthcare targets to detect

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diseases at an early stage and encourage a healthy lifestyle. This was believed to inspire patients to use all the preventive care facilities, to demonstrate that prevention is better than cure. The main motive of this model was to undergo patient activation; there was a conventional system that on the algorithm as an individual needs to visit the hospital or the doctor when they are sick/ in times of need. This is the main thought process that was supposed to be rebated by the value-based care system. From around 300 peer-reviewed medical research documents, it was inferred that patient activation towards preventive care is a habit, which is why it is hard to develop and defeat the whole conventional healthcare industry system which was a habit of visiting the doctor only if needed in an emergency. Usually, at this stage, a physician's care gets limited in most hospice diseases.³

When we talk about the *future of value-based care for preventive care*, we would say that statistically, these preventive care options are not majorly being used, although they are made free and accessible, the response rate from the population is still low. For this problem statement, do we need to mandate certain policies around preventive care for the population to use it? It does sound like a tangible solution, but in a democratic developed nation, it could mean to "force" the population, even if it is for good, even if it is targeting better health outcomes, it doesn't seem like a welcoming idea due to the imposition. So, what can we change for preventive care in this VBC model? Well, it has been noted in several countries, that if the accessibility of the service is quick, it is more likely to be consumed. For instance, people tend to take the Uber/ Lyft cabs more even though buses and trains are cheaper, because of their accessibility, one can book an Uber wherever they are standing, they, however, can't change the location where the bus/ train halts. It's the same with healthcare. Here, in this scenario, digital healthcare with a patient engagement experience could boost performance. Using apps and wearable devices, arranging virtual doctor visits, more home testing options, and building patient health stats dashboard for the patient to be a part of the care team.⁴

VBCs are not typically attended by providers alone, but rather by payers, health care providers, and ancillary service providers. A shared goal of value should align with the stakeholders. Incentives for these stakeholder types are being aligned by shared savings arrangements, which encourage engagement, too. Providers in an ACO include a hospital and nearly 1,000 patients who are served by primary care and specialty physicians. As illustrated in the scenario, multiple stakeholders can share value-based payments to engage them. As an ACO generates savings, resulting bonuses can be distributed in a way that helps all types of providers maintain adequate profit margins.⁸

VBC assumes that stakeholders will be able to reduce costs. Therefore, providers should identify opportunities for improving value before engaging in value-based payment arrangements based on cost or quality. Variations in spending could be improved. There has been plenty of research demonstrating that spending on the same health care service varies by region.⁷

Recommended Solutions:

As we have discussed in the history part, CMS and CMMI have invested a big amount for the generation of dozens of alternatives and its hundreds of tracks. As a leader, CMS should develop a vision for U.S. health care and a roadmap to execute it. This would include a portfolio of accountable care management that is transparent, straightforward, and sustainable. In addition, the increasingly complex landscape of alternative payment models deters providers from adopting them. Providers are prone to seeking small pools of shared savings to motivate them instead of transforming their practices systematically. To identify and expand the highest-performing models, it is difficult to distinguish among overlapping models and their effects on cost and quality. Health systems are uncertain about investing for optimal transformation and return on investment as CMS has not guided the types of value-based models to be sustained

for the long term. By regularly evaluating the effect of the APM portfolio against expectations, CMS can begin to move away from a narrow focus on individual models. The CMS must outline a long-term vision for health care delivery and payment by 2030, including options to fee-for-service arrangements, the design of model financial arrangements, and the management of risk via mandatory participation in insured programs. In general, having a clear strategy and set of goals will allow CMS to slow the introduction of new models, evaluate and phase out under-performing initiatives, and evaluate projected and observed performance. Providers of primary care may be paid capitated fees for care management activities under advanced primary care models. Instead of basing benchmarks on providers' past performance, average costs in a market can be used for the episode and population-based payment. A population-based payment system would be mandatory as the cornerstone of this strategy since it could reduce risk selection and facilitate care coordination. CMS' value-based payment initiatives should be based on a portfolio-based approach to support its overall strategic vision. Portfolio approaches conceive new payments models as investments spanning several APM programs, with specific allocations determined by high-level objectives such as reducing per-beneficiary costs, improving value, and enhancing access to health care. CMS could allocate resources and measure success using such a division of investments.⁸

There is a renewed focus on spreading alternative payment models to address health disparities, uneven quality, and increased healthcare costs. The government needs to work together to develop a high-quality, efficient system. These models must evolve from an experiment into a national standard. Alternative payments as they are implemented today have failed to create large-scale, systemic change in the past decade of experimentation. Nevertheless, rigorous analysis of the lessons learned from both successful and unsuccessful APMs suggests they can improve value by reducing costs and improving quality. In addition, we must enlist late adopters, accelerate APM implementations already in place and working, create

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a value-based payment system that integrates equity, and implement value-based payment policies in commercial insurance. It is both audacious and achievable for a sustainable healthcare system to reward better quality, equity, and efficiency.⁸

To make VBC a sustainable business, plan-provider collaborations and those business enterprises supporting it need to invest in empowering clinicians who can lead the change. A true transformation of VBC will be driven by tools and technologies that are based on the insights gleaned from that work. Innovative technologies and workflows that promote provider success at the point of care will be essential to successful implementations. The final prize will go to the health plans and healthcare providers if they align their priorities with the technology needed to increase the scale and effectiveness of solutions.⁹

Automating administrative inefficiencies caused by VBC can be made more accessible by voice assistants powered by AI. For example, voice technology-assisted physicians in taking medical notes 70% more efficiently using voice assistants: A research study found that physicians using Suki's voice assistant reduced their administrative workload. A care coordination IT system can help reduce penalties for readmissions by streamlining patient management. Technology for transferring patient information across the care continuum is called care coordination IT (CCIT). Improving communication during care transitions could reduce readmissions and the 80% of medical errors that arise because of inadequate communication. Further, with CCIT, providers could prevent wasting money and time on unnecessary treatments and procedures after misdiagnosis.¹⁰

Evaluation of Recommendations:

The recommended solutions that we see, firstly, consider the creation of a roadmap towards the payment model. This would take a longer estimated duration to think upon, secondly, regulations related to healthcare, do not pass quickly. The committee meeting and the

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procedures behind it will expand the lifespan of this project. Moreover, over to implement tools and technology, there are few constraints to it. Such tools need a skilled set of labor and considerable time. Usually, these tools are not compatible with clinical, meaning the way they are designed and are designed by, are a group of people who has a theoretical view of the clinical domain, the tools need development, upgrade, and enhancement over time. Later such software skills and the knowledge of the efficient usage of tools must be provided to the physicians, nurses, and anyone in the care team using it. Hence, there are various levels of certification for tools such as Epic, Cerner, and Meditech.^{6,7} Although we saw that the early adopters from the healthcare physician side are at an advantage, the late adopters need to undergo various administrative barriers; we do talk a little about removing specific barriers to reduce the physician workload. However, we need to also address that this administrative work is crucial, and the data is valued and sometimes used for evaluation purposes. We have seen a large data over physician un-satisfaction when it comes to implementing or upgrading the technology. The introduction of high-end tech like artificial intelligence could bring two possible issues, lack of awareness and data security.⁸ Artificial Intelligence is a type of tool that demands awareness from everyone that encounters it. That means even the patients who might be using it must be aware of its know-how. Artificial Intelligence for the transcription process is highly encouraged, as we can see that it efficiently reduces paper supplies that could be possibly needed saves 70% of the time on average for each nurse performing the data-entry process. When it comes to using high-end machine learning tools for the use of healthcare, for example, IBM Watson AI for healthcare, it does greatly help the physicians with the workload.¹⁰ However, the care team needs to make the patients aware of what a machine can do and what is not within the limit, that is, the patients need to be made aware of the workings of artificial intelligence in the healthcare space.¹⁰ Moreover, an upgraded tech must meet HIPAA compliance tests. Data security and integration are more of case-wise testing; there are certain

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gaps where data could be potentially leaked, the weakest link for this chain being humans, for the health-tech to implement homecare through AI.¹⁰ The goal of value-based care is to send fewer patients to hospitals, which means that practices that are part of hospital systems will be more financially secure, although they are subject to conflicting incentives. The incentives in these systems don't align with taking better care of people, so payers continue to operate in the old way, forgetting the steps to take for the future of value-based care system.¹¹

Peer Review:

Firstly, the peer review, greatly helped me with grammar that various web-based grammar checking apps did not detect. Secondly, by proofreading the material, the flow of the brief policy paper was taken under consideration and updated accordingly, this taught me the importance of proofreading by a third person. Since we get engrossed in writing all the research that is going on from our thought to the paper, the flow is easily misjudged. I was able to trace it back with the review comments. My peer-reviewer and I have worked on a similar topic as, "Artificial Intelligence in Health Informatics", in the last semester for the Introduction to Health Informatics class. Thus, from our similar interests, we were able to derive certain points over the use of AI in for the advancement of the future of the value-based care model. In the article, various examples of bots such as Suki and IBM Watson AI were derived from the same conversation and interest of ours.

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